
Artistry in Narratives: Exploring Literary Devices Using The Author's Toolbox

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Summary— The paper, "Artistry in Narratives: Exploring Literary Devices using the Author's Toolbox," by Divilyn M. Rodriguez, presents an innovative teaching strategy aimed at enhancing the creative writing skills of senior high school students. Recognizing the importance of literary devices in crafting compelling narratives, this innovation addresses the prevalent issue of students' limited mastery in utilizing these tools effectively. The Author's Toolbox combines a structured graphic organizer with a phased instructional process to foster both guided and independent learning. This method aims to provide students with hands-on experiences in identifying and analyzing literary devices in texts, ultimately leading to a deeper appreciation of literature and improved narrative skills. The innovation is structured into three phases: guided class activities, group activities, and independent tasks. Phase 1 involves teacher-led activities where students are introduced to the toolbox and guided in identifying literary devices within provided texts. Phase 2 transitions to group work, combining guided and independent analysis, encouraging collaboration and critical thinking. Phase 3 focuses on individual analysis, preparing students for summative assessments by reinforcing their ability to independently identify and use literary devices. The cyclical nature of these phases ensures that formative assessments inform instructional adjustments, catering to the varying readiness levels of students. The Author's Toolbox is designed not only to improve students' narrative skills but also to align with the Department of Education's vision and mission, emphasizing inclusivity, accessibility, and effective education. The innovation promotes cooperative and collaborative learning, fostering engagement and critical thinking. The phased approach ensures that students gain a comprehensive understanding and mastery of literary devices, essential for success in higher education and various careers.

Keywords— Artistry, Literacy, Independent Learning

I. OVERVIEW

In the Senior High School Humanities strand, Creative Writing is a crucial subject that equips students for success in higher education and future careers. Many students, however, struggle with this skill, as evidenced by their limited use of literary devices in their writing (Rodriguez, 2019). Mastery of these devices is essential, not only for crafting compelling narratives (making them more memorable and thought-provoking for readers) but also for success in fields like literature, communications, journalism, and any career requiring effective written or oral communication. Furthermore, understanding literary devices deepens students' appreciation of literature itself (Yeung, 2021).

To address this need, this paper proposes a novel approach: The Author's Toolbox. This structured learning experience provides a framework for students to explore, identify, and analyze the various literary devices employed by authors. Through a combination of individual and group activities,

this process guides students towards independent practice, ultimately fostering both mastery of the skill and literary appreciation. In essence, The Author's Toolbox creates a synergy between structure and process, leading to a deeper understanding and effective use of literary devices. (Pllana, 2021)

This innovation is aligned to the vision and mission of the Department of Education as spelled out in the Philippine Professional Standard of Teachers (PPST), specifically 1.5.2: apply a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills.

The implementation of the Author's Toolbox innovation embodies the core values and principles of the Department of Education, adhering to inclusivity, accessibility, and effective education. As the Department advocates the values of cooperative and collaborative learning and the principles of hands-on learning, these approaches foster engagement, collaboration, and critical thinking development, ultimately enhancing students' understanding of the concepts and mastery of the skill.

II. INNOVATION DESCRIPTION

The innovation is the use of the Author's Toolbox in three (3) phases: Phase 1: Class Activity, Phase 2: Group Activities, and Phase 3: Independent Activity.

The Author's Toolbox is a simple graphic organizer which presents concepts in a graphical or spatial form. The graphic organizer is composed of quadrants. The number of quadrants depends on the different types of literary devices found in the text; e.g., metaphor, personification, foreshadowing, alliteration, etc.

In the Author's Toolbox, learners are going to explore and identify the different literary devices that the author used in a specific text. Learners will give the headings or labels of each quadrant with the type of literary devices found in the text; e.g., Metaphor, Personification, Foreshadowing, Imagery, etc. Learners will also identify the literary devices; e.g., Personification – "The waves were stirred with pity, and the winds blew softly, as if to comfort her." This provides a hands-on experience allowing learners to see that, like a carpenter, authors also have tools to make their literary work creative.

However, the Author's Toolbox is not just an implementation of a graphic organizer because the innovation carries with it a process. Phase 1 is guided activity, Phase 2 is composed of guided and independent group activities, and Phase 3 is individual activity. These phases are very important as they structure the learning experiences of the students in achieving mastery of the topic and skill. This will help learners gain meaningful experience in the process of analyzing a text and identifying the literary devices as used by authors in their literary works.

The advantages of using the Author's Toolbox lie in its ability to classify or organize into the quadrants the different literary devices that an author used in the text. Using a variety of reading texts or narratives also provides opportunities for learners to explore authors' styles in writing, exploring themes among cultures, and empathy or identity with other people.

While the Author's Toolbox is just a simple graphic organizer, how it is used in different phases makes it far better than other teaching strategies. The combination of the graphic organizer and the different phases makes the synergy effect in the meaningful learning of literary devices. While it is true that there is no "one size fits all" strategy, the idea of combining structure and procedure or process can be a form of contextualized instruction. On the other hand, integrating both cooperative and individual learning activities provides a more holistic learning environment. Thus, students can learn both from collaborative interactions and opportunities for independent thought and exploration.

This is the sample of how the Author's Toolbox looks like (structure).

III. INNOVATION STATEMENT

The goal of the Author's Toolbox is to hone the ability of the students enrolled in the Creative Writing class to craft engaging narratives, create memorable characters, and structure plots effectively. To achieve this goal, learners must be able to use literary devices effectively in their written out-

Fig. 1: Author's Toolbox

puts. This can be achieved when they are provided with hands-on and meaningful experience of identifying the different literary devices that authors use in their craft to captivate readers' attention and keep them engaged throughout the narrative. Creative writers need literary devices to enrich the readers' experience by engaging them, creating vivid imagery, conveying depth and complexity, developing characters, organizing structure, eliciting emotional impact, showcasing style and voice, and fostering critical thinking skills. The inability to use literary devices in writing narratives can lead to decreased reader engagement, limited expressiveness, weak character development, disorganized structure, limited creativity, difficulty conveying themes, and reduced critical thinking skills as reflected in the written narratives. Therefore, it is essential for literature teachers to support students in developing proficiency in using literary devices to enhance their writing skills and deepen their understanding and appreciation of literature.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION PROCEDURE

The process flow and framework of the implementation of this three-phase innovation begins with the careful planning of the narratives that will be used throughout the phases. Narratives should be carefully chosen. Aside from the fact that they should be grade level appropriate, they should be interesting, and rich in literary devices such as figures of speech, flashback, foreshadowing, among others. Then printing of the reading texts and Author's Toolbox activity sheets will follow. Once all materials have been prepared, the teacher now moves to the implementation phases.

Below is a description of how the Author's Toolbox is used in the different phases. Phase 1 is a guided class activity. The teacher gives each student a copy of the narrative. After the discussion on the elements of the story, the teacher introduces to the whole class, the Author's Toolbox which is illustrated on the board. On the Author's Toolbox are quadrants which contain headings with paragraph numbers. The headings are the types of literary devices found in the text such as metaphor, foreshadowing, etc.; the paragraph numbers are guides for the students where these literary devices are found in the text; e.g., Metaphor - paragraph 12. This means that in paragraph 12 there is a metaphor. So, students will look for the metaphor in paragraph 12 and write this sentence or

Fig. 2: Phase 1 Guided Activity

Fig. 3: Independent Activity Phase

phrase under the appropriate quadrant under metaphor; e.g., “She cried with streaming tears.” This experience fosters the process of identifying the literary devices used in the text.

Phase 2 involves guided and independent group activities. Here, the teacher divides the class into groups with five to six members. For the guided group activity, students in groups will be given another narrative to read and discuss. Then the teacher gives a copy of the Author’s Toolbox with the headings and paragraph numbers where the literary devices are found in the selection. Students in groups will identify the phrases or sentences which are literary devices and write these on the Author’s Toolbox. This activity allows cooperation and collaboration among members of the group as they analyze the reading selection to be able to identify the literary devices. For the independent group activity, the teacher will give another reading selection to the groups but this time without the headings and paragraph numbers. Therefore, students in groups will comprehend the text and identify the literary devices. This fosters comprehension, analyzing, and critical thinking. Students in groups collaborate together, sharing their thoughts and ideas, making meaning with the text, language, and style of the authors which will lead to the appreciation of the literary work.

Phase 3 is an individual activity. The teacher asks students to read another narrative. Since the learners will be reading a lot of narratives, choosing relatable themes is very important in sustaining the interest of the learners. In this phase, there are no headings, no more paragraph numbers, no more guides. Each student individually analyzes the text and identifies the literary devices used in the narrative using the Author’s Toolbox. This phase prepares individual learners for the summative assessment.

As provided in DepEd Order No. 8 s. 2018, formative assessment results must be used to provide further instruction. Learners who have not yet gained mastery will be given new sets of reading texts following the same phases. This can be done during their remedial class. Adjustments in the pacing and teaching strategies based on formative assessment results ensure that learners will be ready during the summative assessment. Hence, it is impossible to move on to summative assessment without ensuring mastery through formative assessment.

a. Process Flow Framework

This is how the Author’s Toolbox is used in three phases as shown in the process flow.

The structure in figure 4 is a very simple process that can be followed in the implementation of the innovation. It can be seen that the different phases provide a structure for guided and independent practice. In each phase, learners are actively engaged with the text as they work with others in their group. Learners will bring this experience during the individual activity and summative assessment. Phases 1–3 provide ongoing formative assessments ensuring that learners have mastered the skill before the summative assessment.

The formative assessments provide valuable information to the teacher whether or not students are learning the skill. At the end of Phase 3, where students individually do the activity, the result of their outputs will determine if they have mastered the skill or not. This feedback will prompt the teacher on which direction to take: if the learner has mastered the skill, then that learner is ready for the summative assessment. If the learner has not mastered the skill, then that learner is not ready for the summative assessment. It would be frustrating to continue with summative assessments if the skill has not been learned or mastered.

Therefore, successful summative result is achieved when formative assessment results are used to provide feedback to both teachers and students about learning progress, strengths, and areas needing improvement. This feedback informs instructional decisions, allowing the teacher to adjust teaching strategies, pacing, and content delivery to better meet students’ needs.

In figure 4, it is important to differentiate instruction according to the readiness level of the learners. The new sets of reading materials should be chosen carefully, and regroupings should now consider the readiness level of the learners. Differentiating instruction according to the readiness level of learners is essential for creating a responsive and inclusive learning environment that meets the diverse needs of learners and maximizes their potential for success (Zens, 2021).

Although the formative results have already been used to ensure the mastery of skills for the summative assessment, the flowchart still considers learners who have not mastered the skill even during the summative assessment. This means that remedial instruction is inevitable in the teaching process. Remedial instruction is essential in supporting students, pro-

Fig. 4: Process Flow

moting equity and inclusion, and setting students on the path to academic success. By providing targeted interventions and support, remedial instruction helps ensure that all students have the opportunity to reach their full potential (Yolak, 2019).

b. Project Management

The teacher has the responsibility of managing the implementation of the innovation. The teacher ensures that the goals and objectives of the innovation are met and that learners have full access to the materials.

The project management strategies employed to ensure the successful implementation of the innovation include establishing clear goals, creating a detailed and realistic timeline, allocating resources effectively, and conducting monitoring and evaluation reviews. These strategies help streamline processes, mitigate risks, and ensure that the innovation stays on track to achieve intended outcomes.

While the innovation primarily involves the teacher and the students, collaboration among teachers is highly encouraged. Teachers teaching Creative Writing and 21st Century Literature can work together, assuming roles and responsibilities such as selecting engaging and grade-appropriate reading texts with a variety of literary devices, planning for the printing of reading selections and Author's Toolbox activity sheets, and meeting to discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the innovation and how to modify it to suit the context of their learners.

c. Timeline

The period of implementation of the innovation is two (2) weeks. This includes the pre-implementation, during implementation, and post-implementation stages.

The Pre-implementation stage includes the planning of the four (4) reading selections that will be used and the printing of these materials, including the Author's Toolbox worksheets. The during implementation stage includes the delivery of the reading selections in four (4) sessions. The post-implementation stage includes the assessment and the utilization of the assessment results. This refers to determining

which learners will go on for a remedial class where the cycle of the process flow will be used, with another set of reading selections. The cycle continues until learners have mastered the skill.

The post-implementation stage continues until learners have mastered the skill. It is very crucial as it allows for an assessment of how well the innovation is meeting its intended goals and objectives. By evaluating its effectiveness, teachers can determine whether the innovation is producing the desired outcomes and making a positive impact on teaching and learning.

The post-implementation stage provides an opportunity to identify challenges, barriers, or unexpected issues that have arisen during the implementation phase. Conversely, the teacher can recognize successful steps, best practices, and areas of excellence that can be replicated or expanded upon.

d. Resource Utilization

Successful management of the innovation ensures that all learners have individual copies of the reading text during the activity. The Author's Toolbox activity sheets should also have been provided in groups or individually depending on the phase.

The resources used in the Author's Toolbox innovation include bond paper, flip charts (manila paper), marking pens, masking tape, and a printer, which are readily available in the school.

To ensure cost-effectiveness and sustainability, recycled bond paper can be used for printing the Author's Toolbox activity sheets. Copies of the reading selections can be printed at a ratio of 1:2. Through the use of technology, students can also be provided with the soft copy of the reading selections, although learners exposed to printed materials tend to perform better than those using digital formats (PISA, 2018).

e. Progress Monitoring

In this innovation, the teacher is responsible for monitoring the progress of the implementation and ensuring that the goals and objectives are met. Monitoring also involves tracking learners' performance, including checking their outputs

Below is the Gantt Chart for the implementation:

Task Name	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7	Day 8	Day 9	Day 10
Pre-Implementation: Preparation & Printing of Reading Selections										
Implementation										
Phase 1 Text 1										
Phase 2 Text 2										
Phase 2 Text 3										
Phase 3 Text 3										
Post Implementation										
Summative Test										
Utilization of Assessment Results										

Fig. 5: Gantt Chart

during group and individual activities. Learners must receive feedback on the correctness of their answers to monitor their progress effectively. This formative assessment ensures that learners are gaining mastery of the skill and understanding the process of analyzing texts and identifying literary devices.

Group and individual scores are recorded but not graded. Additionally, the teacher circulates among students to ensure they are on the right track and collects feedback about the task or the innovation. These observations and feedback are documented in a journal for easy reference. Phase 2 provides valuable data on ongoing student learning, informing adjustments to session phasing.

To keep the teacher on track, a Gantt Chart will be used to monitor tasks and implementation dates. A Gantt Chart visually represents the schedule of tasks and activities required to complete a project, illustrating start and end dates and durations. It is a valuable tool for effective planning, scheduling, and management.

Effective progress monitoring is crucial to ensure that the innovation produces the appropriate outputs leading towards achieving its intended outcomes.

Figure 6 shows the promising outcomes of the innovation. Aside from learners acquiring mastery of the desired skill, their writing outputs can be collected to form a class portfolio. Additionally, their literary works can be published in the school paper or publication, showcasing their creativity and achievements.

V. SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

For sustainability, the innovation can be integrated into the school curriculum to ensure alignment with curriculum goals and standards. It should be incorporated into lesson plans, and instructional materials should be developed accordingly. Professional development can be provided through Learning

Actions Cell (LAC) sessions. Allocating sufficient resources is paramount to meet these needs.

Establishing sustained mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the innovation over time is crucial. Findings from these evaluations should be collected to gather feedback, informing continuous improvement efforts to refine practices and make necessary adjustments to enhance the innovation’s effectiveness and sustainability.

Feedback from other teachers who have used the innovation can also be collected to inform future decisions and improvements.

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Innovation Output/Outcomes

Outputs/Outcomes <i>(enumerates the outputs or outcomes produced from this innovation)</i>	Beneficiaries <i>(who benefited from the corresponding results of outcomes)</i>
Accomplished Author's Toolbox activity sheets showing acceptable answers	Grade 12 Creative Writing learners
Understanding and appreciation of literature	
Improved writing skills in writing fiction	
A collection of students' / class literary works	
Publication of literary works in the school publication	

Fig. 6: Gantt Chart